

Dodona

also known as “Oracle of Zeus at Dodona”, “Sanctuary of Zeus at Dodona”

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Dodona in Epirus was reputedly the oldest oracle in ancient Greece. The oracle and its sanctuary were dedicated to Zeus Naios, whose local consort was Dione Naia. References to the oracle go back to the Homeric epics, from which we hear of the Selloi (or Helloi), the prophets who were said to sleep in the sanctuary with unwashed feet (Il. 16.233-35), or of the sacred oak that spoke oracles with the voice of Zeus (Od. 14.327-28 = 19.296-97). In later periods, sources refer to oracular responses being derived from the sound of the wind passing through the leaves of the sacred oak or from the movement of the doves sitting in the tree (Hdt. 2.55). Homer's barefoot Selloi also largely disappear from the historical record, being replaced by the middle of the fifth century BCE by three priestesses known as Peleïades, that is, "Doves" (Hdt. 2.55; Strabo 7.329; Paus. 10.12.10). The oracle typically gave responses to individuals in a private capacity, though it was occasionally consulted officially by states. The standard practice involved the petitioner writing their question on a lead tablet, which received a "yes" or "no" response from the oracle. The popularity of Dodona waxed and waned in antiquity. Though the sanctuary was extremely ancient (archaeological evidence confirms that the site was occupied from the Early Helladic Period, with a sanctuary in use from probably the thirteenth century BCE), the remoteness of Dodona led to the oracle being eclipsed by Delphi in historical times. During the reign of Pyrrhus in the early third century BCE, Dodona became the religious center of Epirus and Macedonia; the Naia Festival, probably celebrated every four years, was established at this time. The site was sacked by the Aetolians in 219 BCE and later suffered after the Roman destruction of Epirus in 167 BCE; though the sanctuary was restored and remained in use in some capacity until the fourth century CE, it never recovered its former importance.

Date Range: 1200 BCE - 392 CE

Region: Dodona

Region tags: Greece

The sanctuary of Dodona, containing the Temple of Zeus Naios as well as the buildings of the greater sanctuary (including temples of several other gods, a theater, and athletic structures).

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: H. W. Parke, *The Oracles of Zeus* (Cambridge: Harvard UP, 1967)
- Source 2: É. Lhôte, *Les Lamelles Oraculaires de Dodone* (Genève: Droz, 2006)
- Source 3: E. Eidinow, *Oracles, Curses, and Risk among the Ancient Greeks* (Oxford: Oxford UP, 2007), esp. pp. 56-138

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.ancient-greece.org/archaeology/dodona.html>
- Source 1 Description: An overview of the archaeology of Dodona

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

- Scientific

Years of excavation:

- Year range: 1873-1875, 1913-1921, 1929-1932, 1950s, 1981-present

Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: Dodona Excavation

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation
- Tree, grove, or forest
- Water source

Notes: The defining feature of the sanctuary and oracle of Zeus at Dodona was the sacred oak, connected to the oracular responses given at the site. Ancient sources also speak of a sacred spring located near the sacred oak. Finally, Dodona was located in the mountainous region of Epirus in northwestern Greece; the site itself, including its acropolis, was commanded by Mount Tomaros.

Type of elevation

- Mountain

Notes: Dodona was located in the mountainous region of Epirus. The site was dominated by Mount Tomaros.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Terracing

– Clearing

– Trackway or road-surface

– Other [specify]: Buildings, temples, athletic facilities, statuary

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Notes: Though not centrally located and considered relatively remote even in antiquity, Dodona was not completely removed from cities ancient or modern. In antiquity, there was a town that arose near the sanctuary. Today, the archaeological site of Dodona is removed from the surrounding cities, though the medium city of Ioannina (the capital of the region of Ioannina in Greece) is not far from the site.

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Notes: Like many sites in ancient Greece, Dodona and its surrounding urban settlements always remained relatively rural; Dodona itself, even at the height of its importance, was never more than modestly urban, and its remote location ensured that the site and its surroundings would always be largely rural.

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Purposefully placed plants

Notes: The main feature of Dodona was a sacred oak of Zeus (and its surrounding grove).

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The structures of Dodona include temples, athletic buildings, and community buildings. These were built or modified over the many centuries the oracle was in use, with major periods of building occurring in the time of Pyrrhus in the early third century BCE, in the time of Philip V of Macedon in the late third century BCE, and in the time of Augustus in the first century BCE.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The features of Dodona--most notably the sacred oak and grove of Zeus--was changed over the period the site was in use. As the site decline, the grove was reduced to just a single tree.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Social

Notes: Dodona became very important as a local religious center in the third century BCE, and Pyrrhus instituted a festival in honor of the local god Zeus Naios.

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Other [specify]: Communal and individual

Notes: Dodona was an ancient and important oracle, and was a site of both communal and individual worship.

– Sacrificial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: The sanctuary of Dodona was destroyed on a few occasions as a result of local political upheaval or war, notably in 219 BCE by the Aetolians and in 167 BCE by the Romans.

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For political reasons

– As the result of war

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

Notes: After the oracle fell into disuse in the fourth century, the site was gradually abandoned and succumbed to the elements.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Zeus Naios

Notes: The sanctuary of Dodona was dedicated principally to Zeus Naios. He was worshiped at the site alongside his local consort Dione Naia. But other secondary gods also had sanctuaries at Dodona.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The origins of the oracle at Dodona are obscure, and likely date to the Mycenaean period. The circumstances under which the site was originally commissioned/built are thus unknown.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– I don't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Notes: Herodotus (2.52-56) records different versions of the myth of Dodona's origins, linking it to the oracle of Zeus Ammon at Siwah. The stories contain supernatural elements (such as speaking doves) but not necessarily divine intervention.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Specify

– Other [specify]: According to Herodotus (2.52-56), Dodona was founded either by kidnapped Phoenician women or at the behest of a speaking dove who came to the site from Egyptian Thebes. According to another mythical tradition, the oracle of Dodona was established by Deucalion and his wife Pyrrha, the survivors of the deluge of Greek myth (see Plutarch, *Life of Pyrrhus* 1).

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The main sanctuary and oracle site was closely connected with an oak tree and surrounding grove used in divination.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The most important structure at the site was the sanctuary of Zeus Naios, the god of the oracle.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 1000

Notes: The theater of Dodona, built by Pyrrhus in the third century BCE, was by far the largest structure of the Dodona sanctuary, dwarfing the rather small temple of Zeus.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 2.8

Notes: Like most ancient Greek stone theaters, the theater of Dodona was built into a hill and was thus naturally elevated. Some structures of the theater, including the proscenium and wall, reached a height of around 2.8 meters.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Substantial use of marble and stone

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Notes: There is ample indication that the sanctuary of Dodona, like all Greek sanctuaries, was decorated with sculpture and relief, indicated archaeologically by traces of sculpture and pedestals discovered at the site.

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human,

anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Notes: There is limited evidence on the decoration of the Dodona sanctuary, though some discoveries include a depiction of Heracles fighting Apollo and of animals such as deer.

Reference: Chapinal-Heras, Diego. Experiencing Dodona. De Gruyter, 2021.
<https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110727593>. p.33

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Substantial statuary and pedimentary decoration, paired with images of gods, humans, animals, plants, and other classical Greek decorative features

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– I don't know

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: The temples of Dodona would have contained cult statues of Zeus, his local consort Dione, and other gods. Little is known about these today.

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: NA

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– I don't know

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: NA

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Notes: Dedicatory statues frequently contained inscriptions.

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The site contains many slave manumissions, not unlike Delphi

↳ Other type of decoration:

– I don't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Zeus Naios and his local consort Dione were represented anthropomorphically in their iconography.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: A few specific features of the Dodona cult, such as oak wreaths, have been attested on iconography of the site (for instance, on coinage).

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Oaks and doves are important iconographic attributes of Dodona

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme deity of Dodona was Zeus, worshiped with the local epiclesis (cult title) of Naios.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some have argued that Zeus Naios as worshiped at Dodona originated as a chthonic deity.

Reference: Lhôte, Éric. *Les Lamelles Oraculaires De Dodone*. Geneva: Droz, 2006. p.407-420

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– Yes

Notes: Epirote elites and rulers commonly traced their descent to Achilles, a mythical grandson of Zeus.

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

Notes: Zeus as worshiped at Dodona became a kind of patron god of the Epirotes and Molossians in the early third century BCE.

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: Zeus was not a monotheistic deity, at least not as typically conceived, though he was the highest god of the Greek pantheon

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Most accounts of divination practices at Dodona stress the role of the sacred oak. Oracles were based on the rustling of the leaves, the movements of the doves, or (as archaeological evidence suggests) on rites involving tripods.

Reference: Chapinal-Heras, Diego. Experiencing Dodona. De Gruyter, 2021.
<https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110727593>. p.114-120

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: One source reports that there were hallucinogenic vapors at Dodona that were used in rituals, but most modern scholars dismiss this (Prudentius, *Apotheosis* 439-444).

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Besides Zeus, other deities worshiped at Dodona included Dione, Themis, Aphrodite, and probably Heracles.

Reference: Chapinal-Heras, Diego. Experiencing Dodona. De Gruyter, 2021.
<https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110727593>. p.107-113

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Dione and Themis (and probably Apollo as well) were invoked together with Zeus in divination at Dodona.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Divination was the main way Zeus was thought to communicate with worshippers at Dodona; less is known about the other gods worshiped at the site

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Notes: Zeus Naios would have had a cult statue in his temple at Dodona, though the statue does not survive and little is known about it today.

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cult statue hidden:
 - No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:
 - Yes

- ↳ Libations:
 - Yes [specify]: normally wine

- ↳ Offerings of food:
 - Yes [specify]: meat (sacrificed animals)

- ↳ Animal sacrifice:
 - Yes [specify]: oxen, goats

- ↳ Human sacrifice:
 - No

- ↳ Sacred objects:
 - Yes [specify]: various ceremonial objects, especially tripods

- ↳ Daily life objects:
 - Yes [specify]: incense, water, other votives

- ↳ Other:
 - Other [specify]: oak wreaths

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: Priesthoods were assigned based on sex (Selloi were male, Peleiades were female)

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: There is limited information on the rituals performed by the priests at Dodona or by those who came to consult the oracle, though purification rituals are not unlikely (they were common at other sanctuaries, such as Delphi)

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: There were many rituals practiced at Dodona, including rites pertaining to divination, sacrifice, processions, and the festival of Zeus Naios (the Naia).

Reference: Chapinal-Heras, Diego. Experiencing Dodona. De Gruyter, 2021.
<https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110727593.p.120-127>

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Uncertain, though the theater of Dodona could hold over 15000 spectators

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Varies (the festival of Zeus Naios probably took place every four years, but other rituals were more frequent)

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: As in Delphi, ritual processions and sacrifices would take place, functionally upholding a common ritual orthopraxy

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: bulls, sheep

Notes: Bulls were commonly sacrificed to Zeus; bull and sheep sacrifices at the sanctuary of Zeus Naios are attested in ancient literature (Demosthenes 21.53). Bull sacrifices at Dodona have been conjectured on the basis on numismatic evidence. Archaeologists have also unearthed animal bones, especially bovine bones, at the site, and these are most likely connected to animal sacrifice.

Reference: Dakaris, Sotirios. *Archaeological Guide to Dodona*. Ionnina: Cultural Society, 1971. p.157-158

Are there human sacrifices:

– No

Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Valuable objects such as cauldrons and tripods have been discovered at Dodona, and many of these were votive offerings.

Reference: Dieterle, Martina. *Dodona: Religionsgeschichtliche Und Historische Untersuchungen Zur Entstehung Und Entwicklung Des Zeus*. Hildesheim: Olms, 2007.

Reference: Chapinal-Heras, Diego. *Experiencing Dodona*. De Gruyter, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110727593>. p.30-34, passim

Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Weapons, shields, and tools have been attested as votive offerings at Dodona.

Reference: Chapinal-Heras, Diego. Experiencing Dodona. De Gruyter, 2021.
<https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110727593>. p.33-34

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: NA

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Notes: Maintenance of the site appears to have been performed by the priestesses of the sanctuary.

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The site was destroyed and reconstructed on a few occasions.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: There were permanent priests and priestesses at the site whose duties most likely included routine maintenance

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrims usually came to Dodona to consult the oracle, but other motivations are attested, including taking part in festivals and processions.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:
– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
– Yes

Notes: Consultations of the oracle were often connected with life events such as marriage, illness, and childbirth.

↳ Birth
– Yes

↳ Transition to adulthood
– Yes

↳ Death
– Yes

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Slavery, business, illness, etc.

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
– Yes

Reference: Chapinal-Heras, Diego. Experiencing Dodona. De Gruyter, 2021.
<https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110727593.p.134-144>

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:
– Yes

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Notes: Feasts would have been held at Dodona in honor of festivals such as the Naia or even in honor of public consultations of the oracle.

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: It is likely that banquets and feasts were held at the building known as the Bouleuterion.

Reference: Emmerling, T.. Studien Zu Datierung, Gestalt Und Funktion Der "kultbauten" Im Zeus-heiligtum Von Dodona. Hamburg: Dr. Kovac, 2012. p.222-23

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Notes: The Naia festival, in honor of Zeus Naios and Dione, was the main festival celebrated at Dodona. It was probably celebrated every four years in the month of Apellaios (September/October). The festival included athletic and musical competitions. The festival is usually regarded as having been instituted in the third century BCE by Pyrrhus, but there is some evidence that it originated as early as the fifth century BCE.

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Probably every four years for the Naia

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

↳ Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Requires new construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The theater and stadium at Dodona would have been necessary for the athletic contests that were part of the Naia festival.

- ↳ Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
 - number: 15000-20000 (capacity of the theater)
- ↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
 - Yes
- ↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:
 - Elites
 - Non-elites
 - Religious professionals

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

- ↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

 - No
- ↳ Divination through human communication:
 - Yes

Notes: People who came to consult the Dodona oracle conveyed their petitions or questions by writing them on lead tablets.

 - ↳ Is a human being the vehicle for the oracle:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Is a human being the interpreter of the oracle:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified sex/gender:
 - Yes

Notes: The priests at Dodona were female (though priests may have originally be male, as reference to the Selli or Helli in the Homeric epics suggests).

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: It seems that the priests of Dodona were typically locals.

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified class:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is sex-deprivation required:

– No

↳ Are intoxicants required:

– No

↳ Physical ordeal required:

– No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:

– Yes

Notes: One of the ways divination was practiced at Dodona was by interpreting the movements of the doves who lived in the sacred grove.

↳ Wild-animals

– Yes

↳ Domesticated animals

– No

↳ Captive animals

– No

↳ Divination through non-living material:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: One of the ways divination was practiced at Dodona involved the sacred oak tree of Zeus Naios. Oracles seem to have been based on the sound of the wind rustling the leaves of the tree (though there are mythical references to the tree, or parts of it, speaking with the

voice of the god).

Other

– Other [specify]: References to hallucinogenic trances as part of divination at Dodona are probably inaccurate.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is one reference (Pausanias, Description of Greece 2.27.3) to pilgrims visiting the site to be healed, but this was not typical of how the sanctuary was used (and was reportedly not always successful).

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: Ancient sources refer to priests at Dodona known as Selloi or Helloi as well as three old female priestesses known as Peleiades ("Doves"). It is likely that the Selloi were the original priests of the site while the Peleiades were added later.

Reference: Chapinal-Heras, Diego. Experiencing Dodona. De Gruyter, 2021.
<https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110727593.p.102-104>

Present full time

– Yes

Present part time

– No

Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: The Homeric epics mention a class of (male) priests known as Selloi or Helloi in connection with Dodona, while later sources speak primarily of a class of (female) priestesses known as Peleiades ("Doves"). It is possible that the male and female priesthoods coexisted, with the female Peleiades gradually becoming more important than the male Selloi.

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
 - Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is limited evidence on the livelihoods of the priests and priestesses at Dodona, though ancient sources sometimes spoke of the Selloi as choosing to live in poverty (Philostratus, *Imagines* 2.33).

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: It was common for Greek sanctuaries to act as landholders and lease out neighboring land to increase profits. There is very limited evidence that Dodona engaged in this practice, largely based on a 4th-century-BCE plaque describing some land that had been donated to the Dodona sanctuary. It has also been argued that Dodona was involved in regional banking activities.

Reference: Chapinal-Heras, Diego. Experiencing Dodona. De Gruyter, 2021.
<https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110727593.p.208-215>

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out land:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:
– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:
– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):
– Yes

Notes: Communal gatherings, including symposia and festivals, took place at Dodona.
Manumissions were also attested at Dodona.

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):
– No

↳ Function for water management:
– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Site served as a major regional (Epirote) religious, social, and athletic hub

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Epigraphic records discovered at Dodona discuss the sanctuary's role in civil life, including its role in manumission and conferring citizenship and other privileges.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

Entry/Answer References

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<https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110727593>. p.33, p.33-34, p.30-34, passim, p.120-127, p.114-120, p.107-113, p.134-144, p.102-104, p.208-215

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